

Physic-informed machine learning for centerless grinding optimization

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Abstract— Centerless grinding is a machining process characterized by highly nonlinear dynamics, large model uncertainty and considerable sensitivity to process parameters. Guaranteeing quality of the worked parts, basically roundness, and short processing time by an optimal process setup is typically a specialized and time-consuming task. In this work, an approach is presented for centerless grinding parameters setup and optimization based on physic-informed machine learning techniques. The real data for model training are provided both as measurements on the ground workpieces and as on-line monitoring signals. The developed functionalities concur in implementing the concept of “intelligent grinding machine”, proposed by Monzese srl, an innovative SME operating in machine tools sector.

Keywords—Centerless grinding, intelligent machine, physic-informed machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the increasing demand of high-quality products, together with the pressure towards flexibility, batch size reduction and the consequent request of fast process reconfiguration, raise the need of automatic and fast process parameters selection/optimization during the setup phase.

The paradigm of Intelligent Machines is expected to cope with this challenge [1]. It defines a new generation of machine tools that are smarter, widely accessible, more adaptive and more autonomous. In particular, these machines entail advanced functionality such as self-awareness, self-maintenance and self-optimisation. With regard to latter functionality, the present work focuses on centerless grinding process (and corresponding machine), aiming at the selection of the parameters that guarantee a suited workpiece (WP) quality, in terms of roundness, exploiting also on-line monitoring, to increase effectiveness and robustness of parameters optimization.

Differently from the on-center version, in centerless grinding the WP is supported on 3 lines by the grinding wheel, the control wheel (that drags the WP assuring its proper rotation) and the work rest, also called supporting blade. Even though this holding system makes the loading/unloading procedure very efficient, it introduces potential problems in terms of process stability and roundness [2], being prone to generate pieces with a wavy profile.

Optimization strategies for grinding operations have been designed by many authors in the literature. In their comprehensive review, Rowe et al. [3], show that most of them relies on Artificial Intelligence (AI). Among these techniques, two families are identified: in the first one desktop systems assist tool and parameters selection, while, in the second ones, self-optimizing systems are integrated within the machine controller. AI methods often exploit black box models. In fact, black box machine learning models (typically neural networks) are currently being used for high-stakes

decision making throughout many industrial processes sectors.

Unfortunately, pure AI data-driven techniques require large datasets to learn properly the behavior of centerless grinding process, which is extremely non-smooth in the parameters space. These large datasets are often unavailable, in the small batch industrial scenario. On the other side, Physic-based (PB) models could be affected by modelling errors and be sensible to parameters uncertainty. On these premises, hybrid solutions, combining the generality of PB models with a data-driven tuning on the specific context, appear to be a promising trade-off [4]. Furthermore, the AI component can intervene in the form of a gradual error compensation, while a basic perfectible optimizer is immediately operating, even in absence of field data.

On these premises, a novel process optimizer is proposed for centerless grinding operations, in the form of a Decision Supporting System. It relies on hybrid physics-informed AI models able to guide the machine tool operator by predicting in advance the performance resulting from a given process parameters set and suggesting the best one. The model is continuously growing in “intelligence” by learning from the workpieces quality measurements that operators can provide it, but also by estimating this quality thanks to virtual sensors fed by the related physical sensors signals (typically Acoustic Emission (AE) sensors and machine signals like torque and position).

II. PROPOSED SOLUTION

A. Specifications

The specifications for the process optimizer implementing the “Intelligent machine” can be derived from Fig. 1. The software receives in input some characteristics of the machine and the targeted process:

- Diameter and characteristics of the working wheel;
- Diameter and characteristics of the control wheel;
- Diameter and material of the workpiece ;
- Part specifications (e.g., final roundness, initial roundness and pre-existing number of lobes, reference cycle time, ...);
- Angle of the support blade;
- Relative static and dynamic compliance between working wheel and control wheel;
- Preferential harmonic component (ie, number of lobes) of the residual roundness error. Note: it is not always possible to guarantee the presence of the desired harmonic.

Then, the optimizer suggests the values of the following parameters:

- Radial feed;
- Support height;
- Work rotational speed;
- If it is impossible to obtain the desired result by varying the aforementioned parameters, the software may require the blade angle to be changed, entailing a manual intervention by the operator.

Fig. 1. Scheme of Intelligent Centerless Grinding SW usage

As soon as work pieces measurements become available (for instance, according to a prescribed quality control policy concerned with roundness KPI), the optimizer can be fed with real data, so that the underlying process model can be trained for a higher prediction accuracy. Moreover, the optimizer is also fed with sensors monitoring data, becoming able to classify the condition of the process and the work piece even when a roundness measure is not available.

B. Solution outline

The off-line roundness optimization is based on a parametric model of the process. Unluckily, a comprehensive process model is very complex, as several aspects concur in determining the final process performance, besides the aforementioned process parameters considered in input. All these factors should be taken into account in overall process optimization with a robust approach, in order to reach accurate results. On the other side, deriving a quality prediction physic-based? model that accounts for such complexity is very challenging [5].

Aiming at conjugating the maximum level of promptness, generality and interpretability of PB models with the adaptation capability of AI, approaches to obtain grey-box (GB) models based on data-driven compensations of PB models have been investigated. The roundness prediction given by a PB model is used as a feature to enhance the training of a black-box (BB) model. In the exploitation phase, the identified GB model is used to drive a classical optimization program from an initial parameter set provided by the operator.

The main optimization strategy follows the schematic of Fig. 2. The roundness predicted by the GB model (r_pred) is minimized in order to comply with a prescribed quality category (c_pred , defined by a threshold on the roundness value). If the prescribed quality is fulfilled, the grinding operation can be attempted. Then, a work piece measurement can be executed, that could confirm or deny the predictions and the optimization result. Anyway, the new measurement

is integrated in GB data set and used to trigger the model retraining.

Fig. 2. Process optimization strategy

An alternative approach could take into account the sole quality category, leaving out the minimization of the continuous roundness value. For this purpose, a dedicated semi-supervised physics-informed classifier has been developed [6].

Fig. 3. Details of Monza KZN, the Intelligent Machine.

III. CONCLUSIONS

A novel approach to optimize centerless grinding process has been conceived, able to merge the *a priori* physical domain knowledge about grinding, with the learning capability and flexibility of AI. It relies on a physic-informed Neural Network model or, in alternative, on a physic-informed semi-supervised classifier. The resulting functionalities concur in concretizing the paradigm of *Intelligent Machine Tool*.

The Intelligent Machine Tool (deployed in Monza KZN centerless grinder, see Fig. 3) will allow a set up process quicker and easier to use, even by less experienced operators, compared to today manual setup. Thanks to the proposed monitoring, ML and optimization architecture, it will be able to manage a large amount of process and quality data, providing a formalized process control and optimization. The work is framed in the more general effort toward new production systems, designed with a high degree of autonomy and adaptation capability. Additionally, it will improve the overall safety, since today set-up procedure typically requires the operator to supervise closely the process, with increased risk of accidents.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge Regione Lombardia and Tech Fast Innovation program, which provided the funds for the development of the present research (Bando Tech Fast, CUP E79J22000010007).

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